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Research Article

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF MICRO SPHERES OF DILTIAZEM HYDROCHLORIDE

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Abstract:

Microspheres of diltiazem hydrochloride were formulated using combination of HPMC and Eudragit RS 100 and Eudragit RS 100 alone by solvent evaporation and nonsolvent addition methods with aim to prolong its release. Six formulations prepared by using different drug;polymer ratios were evaluated for percentage entrapment .loading efficiency, percentage of encapsulation, particle size distribution, scanning electron microscopy, Differential scanning calorimetry infrared spectroscopy, dissolution studies and compared with marketed SR capsules. Depending upon the drug to polymer ratio, the entrapment, loading and encapsulation were found to be 77.45±0.22 to 91.08 ±0.62%,34.76± 0.15 to 52.46±0.25% and 66.09± 0.19 to 82.70 ±0.57 respectively. The microspheres were spherical, discrete and compact and size ranged between 4µm to 24µm. Invitro studies were carried out at different pH for a period of 12 hours and compared with marketed formulation (SR). First order of drug release was followed by formulations using the combination of the retardants and zero order for preparations containing Eudragit RS 100 alone The analysis of regression values of Higuchi plot and koyser-peppas plot and “n” values of koyser – peppas model shows a combination of diffusional and dissolutional mechanism indicating the drug release from the formulations is controlled by more than one process.Results of FTIR and DSC proves that drug polymer interaction was absent. Invivo pharmacokinetic study of the formulation proved that prolongation of drug release is obtained by formulating as micro spheres.

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INTRODUCTION:

Diltiazem hydrochloride, a calcium channel blocker used in the treatment of arrhythmia, angina pectoris and hypertension must be administered t.i.d/b.i.d. Prolonged release dosage forms are designed to complement the pharmaceutical activity of the medicament in order to achieve the longer duration of action there by reducing dosing frequency and improving patient's compliance. Treatment for hypertension is a long term therapy where non compliance is high, hence prolonged release dosage forms are useful for quality health care. Sustained therapeutic action is necessary for alleviating patient's symptoms.

The present study deals with the design and evaluation of microspheres of diltiazem hydrochloride for prolonged release. There are continuing efforts to improve its pharmaceutical formulation in order to optimize therapy. These efforts have been focused on development of oral sustained release preparations.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Diltiazem hydrochloride (Gift sample - Mano Pharmaceuticals, Chennai) Eudragit RS 100(colorcorn). All other chemicals used were of analytical grade. 12 male white rabbits weighing about 2.8 Kg to 3.1Kg were used in vivo study.

Preparation of Micro spheres:

All the formulations were prepared according formulae given in table 1.

Preparation of micro spheres with Eudragit RS100 and HPMC .

Solvent evaporation method was adopted for preparing formulations I,II,III which contain both EudragitRS100 and polyethylene glycol 6000. EudragitRS100 and HPMC in same ratio (0.5g or 1g or 1.5g) was dissolved in 30 ml of acetone to form homogenous polymer solution. Diltiazem hydrochloride (1g) was then added to the polymer solution. The resulting solution was then poured in to beaker containing 300 ml of liquid paraffin while stirring. Stirring was continued for an hour, until acetone evaporated completely. After evaporation of acetone, the micro spheres formed were collected by filtration, washed 4-5times with petroleum ether and dried at room temperature for 24 hours.¹

Preparation of micro spheres with Eudragit RS100

Coacervation - phase separation by the addition of non-solvent was followed for formulations IV ,V,VI. Eudragit RS100 (0.5g or 1g or 1.5g) was dissolved in 50ml of warm toluene to get homogenous polymer solution. Diltiazem hydrochloride (1g) was then added to the polymer solution and mixed thoroughly with the aid of mechanical stirrer for 10 minutes. Coacervation

was then induced by the addition of 30ml of petroleum ether slowly over a period of 20minutes while stirring at the same speed. Stirring was continued for 15 minutes to rigidize the coating of the micro spheres. The encapsulated product was then collected by filtration and dried at room temperature for 24 hours. .²

Determination of drug entrapment in microspheres: 100mg of micro spheres was triturated with distilled water in a glass mortar and pestle .The volume made up to 100 ml with distilled water and it was kept in bath sonicator for 2 hours. Then it was filtered to remove debris and the absorbance was measured by using SHIMADZU UV- Visible spectrophotometer (UV-1601) at 236 nm. Quantative estimation of diltiazem hydrochloride was calculated by using standard graph of diltiazem hydrochloride in distilled water.³ The results in Table 1.

Determination of drug loading and encapsulation efficiency:The diltiazem hydrochloride loading in microspheres was estimated using the formula, $L = \frac{Q_m}{W_m} \times 100$, where L is percentage of loading of micro spheres, W_m is weight of the micro spheres, Q_m is quantity of the drug present in W_m of micro spheres. The amount of drug encapsulation in the micro spheres was determined using the formula, $E = \frac{Q_p}{Q_t} \times 100$, E is percentage of encapsulation of micro spheres, Q_p is the product of drug content per g of microspheres and yield of microspheres in g.⁴ The results in Table 1.

Invitro release studies: Invitro release profile of diltiazem hydrochloride from micro spheres was examined in pH 1.2 buffer from 0-2 h, in pH 4.5 buffer from 2 to 4 h and in phosphate buffer of pH 7. 2 from 4 to 12 h using the rotating basket method specified in USP XXI at 100 rpm. Micro spheres equivalent to 90 mg of drug were placed in the basket and the medium was maintained at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. 10 ml of samples were withdrawn periodically at intervals of one hour and same volume of fresh medium was replaced. The concentration of the drug released at different time intervals was determined by measuring the absorbance at 236 nm.⁵ Figure No. 1 shows the results

Release Kinetics: Data obtained from dissolution studies was fitted to various kinetic equations. The kinetics models used were a zero order equation⁶ ($Q = Q_0 - k_0t$), first order equation⁷ ($\ln Q = \ln Q_0 - k_1t$) and Higuchi's equation⁸ ($Q = k_h t^{1/2}$), Koyser peppas equation⁴ $\log Q_t$ vs $\log t$. Where Q_t is the cumulative amount of drug released at time t and Q_0 is the initial amount of drug present in micro spheres. k_0 is zero order

release rate constant, k_1 is first order release rate constant, and k_h is diffusion rate constant.

Particle Size Analysis and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM): Particle size analysis was carried out by optical microscopy. About 200 micro spheres were selected randomly and their Size were determined using optical microscope fitted with a standard micrometer scale. For formulation exhibiting best in vitro release profile SEM was carried out.⁴

FT-IR analysis and Differential scanning calorimetric(DSC) analysis: Infrared spectra of F-IV was recorded on Boman MB-II FT-IR spectrometer. DSC thermo gram of F-IV was recorded on a scanning calorimeter equipped with a thermal analysis data system (Perkin-Elmer DSC-7).⁴

Results and Discussion: Microspheres were prepared using combination of HPMC and Eudragit RS 100 and Eudragit RS 100 alone by solvent evaporation and non solvent addition techniques respectively. Prepared micro spheres were evaluated for drug entrapment, drug loading and encapsulation efficiency. The drug entrapment was maximum in F-VI to an extent of $91.08 \pm 0.62\%$, drug loading was maximum in F-IV to an extent of $52.46 \pm 0.25\%$, drug encapsulation was maximum in F-VI to an extent of 82.70 ± 0.57 . Dissolution test established that increases polymer concentration decreases rate of drug release from the microspheres. Comparison of dissolution pattern of test formulations with marketed diltiazem hydrochloride sustained release capsules. Showed that F-VI exhibited similar release pattern of marketed SR capsules.

log percentage of drug remaining versus time curves exhibited straight line for the formulations(I,II,III,) prepared with combination of PEG 6000 and Eudragit RS 100 and confirmed that the release rates followed first order. Cumulative percentage of drug release versus time curves exhibited straight line for the formulations(IV,V,VI,) prepared with Eudragit RS 100 alone and confirmed that the release rates

followed zero order. Cumulative percentage of drug release versus square root of time curves shows linearity and it proves that all the formulations follows Higuchi model (Fig no 3) suggesting that release may follows, diffusion mechanism of drug release. The correlation values of Higuchi's plot of formulation VI and diltiazem hydrochloride SR capsule were found to be 0.9697 and 0.9616 respectively. log cumulative percentage of drug release versus log time curves shows high linearity and it proves that all the formulations follows Koysler-peppas model(Fig no4). The correlation values of Koysler-peppas plot of formulation VI and diltiazem hydrochloride marketed SR capsule were found to be 0.9864 and 0.9877 respectively. The slope values of Koysler-peppas plot of formulation VI and diltiazem hydrochloride marketed SR capsule were found to be 0.6448 and 0.0.7016 respectively. The diffusional exponent of release profile (slope) has a value of 0.6447($n > 0.5$), which indicates a zero order release controlled by non Fickian diffusion.

The analysis of regression values of Higuchi plot and koysler-peppas plot and "n" values of koysler-peppas model shows a combination of diffusional and dissolutional mechanism indicating the drug release from the formulations is controlled by more than one process.

The particle size of F-VI microspheres was found to be in the range of $4\mu\text{m}$ to $24\mu\text{m}$. The surface morphology and the internal textures of prepared microspheres observed under a scanning electron microscopy, shows good spherical geometry as evidenced by the SEM photographs(Fig no2). The microspheres were discrete, spherical and uniform. Determination of interaction between drug and polymer were performed using FT-IR and by DSC for F-VI. FT-IR spectra study show no change in the finger print of pure drug spectra, thus confirming absence of drug to polymer interactions(Fig no5 and 6). A sharp endotherm was observed for F-VI at 213.17°C (Fig no7). This melting endotherm was also observed for diltiazem hydrochloride micro spheres at 212.32°C (Fig no8) indicating absence of drug to polymer interactions.

TABLE 1: VALUES OF DRUG ENTRAPMENT,LOADINGAND ENCAPSULATION.

Formulation	Drug: HPMC : EudragitRS100	Drug entrapment Mean \pm S.D. %	Drug loading(%) Mean \pm S.D.	Drug encapsulation(%) Mean \pm S.D.
F-I	1:0.25:0.25	77.45 \pm 0.22	51.63 \pm 0.15	66.09 \pm 0.19
F-II	1:0.5:0.5	83.06 \pm 0.61	41.53 \pm 0.30	74.76 \pm 0.54
F-III	1:0.75:0.75	86.96 \pm 0.40	34.76 \pm 0.15	79.96 \pm 0.35
F-IV	1:0:0.5	78.72 \pm 0.38	52.46 \pm 0.25	68.73 \pm 0.33
F-V	1:0:1	85.33 \pm 0.30	42.66 \pm 0.15	77.65 \pm 0.27
F-VI	1:0:1.5	91.08 \pm 0.62	36.53 \pm 0.15	82.70 \pm 0.57

Fig No 1: In Vitro release of Diltiazem hydro chloride from micro spheres**Fig No 2: SEM photograph of formulation VI**

Fig No 3:Higuchi's plot for Diltiazem hydro chloride micro spheres

Fig No 4:Peppas's plot for Diltiazem hydro chloride micro spheres

Fig No 5: FTIR Spectrum of Diltiazem hydrochloride pure drug

Fig No 6: FTIR Spectrum of Diltiazem hydrochloride microspheres

Fig No 7: DSC Thermogram of Diltiazem hydrochloride pure drug

Fig No 8: DSC Thermogram of Diltiazem hydrochloride microspheres

REFERENCES:

1. Ahmed V., Sharma S., Bhatt P. Formulation and Evaluation of Sustained Release Tablet of Diltiazem Hydrochloride. *Int. J. Pharm. Sci. Res.* 2020;11:2193-2199.
2. Kavishetti R., Halkeri M., Nargund S.L., Shahapur A. Formulation and Evaluation of Mucoadhesive Tablets of Diltiazem Hydrochloride. *World J. Pharm. Pharm. Sci.* 2024;13:1022–1037.
3. Allaboun H., Alkhamis K.A., Al-Nimry S.S. Preparation of Sustained Release Formulation of Verapamil Hydrochloride Using Ion Exchange Resins. *AAPS PharmSciTech.* 2023;24:1–10.
4. Subedi G., Shrestha A.K., Shakya S. Study of Effect of Different Factors in Formulation of Micro and Nanospheres with Solvent Evaporation Technique. *Open Pharm. Sci. J.* 2016;3:182–195.
5. Sahoo J., Mishra B., Kumar Biswal P., Dixit P.K. Formulation, Evaluation and in-Vitro Release Study of Diltiazem Hcl Loaded Gelatinous Microsphere. *Biopharm. J.* 2016;2016:27–33.
6. Krishan B.V., Rao C.B., Kishore V.S. Design and Development of Pulsatile Drug Delivery of Diltiazem Hydrochloride. *Res. J. Pharm. Tech.* 2020;13:2315..
7. Kalidindi DV: Microspheres of diltiazem hydrochloride by ionotropic gelation technique. *Int J Pharm Sci Res* 2017; 8(3): 1413-19.
8. Gupta MK, Khunteta A, Optimization of the release kinetics of diltiazem hydrochloride from tableted microspheres, *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics.* 2018; 8(1):57-63.
9. U.D. Shivhare, S.B. Patel. Emulsification-Internal Gelation Technique for Formulation and Evaluation of Mucoadhesive Microspheres of Diltiazem Hydrochloride. *Research J. Pharm. and Tech.* 2011; 4(9): 1422-1427.